

OXYGEN EVOLUTION REACTION BY USING PHOTOANODIC Ta_3N_5 FOR WATER SPLITTING PROCESS BY DIFFERENT SURFACE MODIFICATION: A REVIEW

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Abstract

Fossil energy is a widely used energy source these days, but because of the fossil usage; many complications also arise. In response, a global shift toward sustainable and renewable energy sources has amplified interest in photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting as a viable route for clean hydrogen production. Water splitting, which involves the decomposition of water into hydrogen and oxygen, depends critically on the development of efficient and stable semiconductor photoanodes. For this reason, many semiconductors are used; but titanium nitride (Ta_3N_5) semiconductor has great importance because of the low-over potential, better band structure, lesser charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), decreased solution resistance (R_s), maximum current density and abundance. However, the practical application of Ta_3N_5 is limited by poor charge mobility, surface instability, and rapid electron-hole recombination. To overcome these limitations, significant research has been carried out to prepare the nanocomposites of Ta_3N_5 such as nanofibers, nanofilms, micro sheets, dum bell-like nanostructures, and nanoflowers. These varied morphologies not only enhance visible-light harvesting and charge separation but also lower overpotential and suppress recombination losses, thus improving the overall efficiency of PEC water splitting. Furthermore, a variety of synthetic methodologies including hydrothermal, sol-gel, electrospinning, electrochemical, precipitation, and chemical reduction techniques helped in achieving uniform doping, nanoscale control, and enhanced structural stability. In conclusion, Ta_3N_5 is of significant interest in semiconductor research for water splitting applications. However, future research must focus on improving long-term operational stability, enhancing charge transport across interfaces, and integrating Ta_3N_5 into tandem PEC cells or hybrid solar fuel systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environment is polluted as fossil fuels are used widely as a major energy source that leads to the global warming and other complications. Another

alarming complication is the limited fossil fuels that are being used on daily basis to meet the energy requirements [1]. Solar energy is abundant source of energy. Semiconductor

photoelectrochemical cells (PEC) is widely used to convert solar energy into chemical energy which is called as STH to reduce world energy problems. Fossil energy is the biggest energy source these days, but as World is shifting to renewable energy source as solar and specifically fuels which is Hydrogen by PEC to get water splitting shows a renewable energy [2]. To convert solar energy into chemical energy, water splitting through solar is a better mean to sort out the power crises.

It is common fact regarding the usage of fossil energy in the region could also lead to the various issues, as it brings pollutants to the environment like the Sulphur dioxide, and Nitrogen dioxide which are the basic cause of the acid rain, and everyone is familiar with the negative impacts of the acid rain in the environment [3]. Many complications have come to the surface like different cyclones in different countries of the world, melting of the glaciers due to the greenhouse effect that have caused severe flood in different regions of India and Pakistan back in the year of 2022. Therefore, World is shifting from the non-renewable energy source to the renewable energy source to fulfil the energy requirements of the World. For the energy production by eco-friendly environment is made possible because of many ways like the wind energy, hydropower, geothermal and solar energy sources etc are the main energy sources in this world.

1.2 Effects of Fossil consumption

Existence of the humankind on this planet is only way possible if the clear source of energy is available, then it is a way possible for the stable life [4]. There are many ways to get the energy, for many years, only reliable was the fossil energy. Fossil energy is carbon-based materials [5]. These fossil fuels are the main cause of the environmental hazards, as rising level of CO₂, heat and other pollutions [6]. It is the major source of the global warming, as the CO₂ increases, it brings the temperature to 0.5 °C rise every 2 to 3 years [7]. Fossil fuels burning in the automobiles, causes the emission source of the acid rain. So the major shift is required from non-renewable energy source to the renewable energy source as reported in the study given by [8]. It is stated that the global energy

supply was 16.7 TW in 2007 according to the energy data [9]. This energy demand has increased, as the World population is increasing day by day [10]. As the World population would reach 9.5 billion in 2050, as this addition in population would also increase the demand of the energy [11]. Energy supply would not be fulfilled by carbon-based fossil fuels, there alternative ways to produce and utilize energy is very important. The energy supply of the World would be 30 TW in 2050. This increase from 16 TW to 30 TW, requires more sources of energy [12]. This low energy supply by the biomass consumption, secondly nuclear energy requires more sites that are difficult to build by that year. If the only reliable source would be fossil fuels, then the level of atmospheric CO₂ would also be doubled [13].

1.3 Renewable Energy shift

Therefore, the better and reliable source is sun, as the sunlight is the only renewable energy source that can meet the energy crises of the World [14]. The major challenge is the harvesting of the sunlight radiations, like to convert she solar energy into the chemical energy. Therefore, the solar panels are widely used cells to harvest the solar energy [15].

Water splitting process was basically introduced to World by Fujishima and Honda in 1972 which led to the new ways of producing energy. Fossil fuels were majorly used to meet the energy problems of the World, and in the same year, Fujishima and Honda performed the Hydrogen evolution with the help of the semiconductor titanium oxide [16]. Since then, huge work has been done on the photoanodes for the effective semiconductors to absorb the maximum visible light better electrical and conduction.

Solar energy is the abundant source of energy on the planet Earth, and semiconductor photoelectrochemical cells (PEC) are widely used to convert the solar energy to the chemical energy i.e. Hydrogen by water splitting [17]. Main anodes that are being used for the water splitting have great importance regarding the effectiveness and firmness [15]. It is reported that sunlight which reaches the earth's surface is 8.6×10^4 TW which is much more than the annual consumption of

energy by human being that is close to 19 TW [18]. Sunlight comprised half of the visible light spectrum whose wavelength range exists from 300-800 nm. It is the major portion of the sunlight so to use the wavelength of this range is quite accomplishable [16].

1.4 Hydrogen as the Important Energy source

Hydrogen can be consumed as the catalyst in the chemical and petroleum industry as a reducing agent. It is reported in study that hydrogen is produced 50 megatons in the world every year, but all this is produced by non-renewable and renewable energy sources [19]. The world is trying to meet the energy requirements, so hydrogen can also be obtained by the other renewable methods like the water splitting by thermochemical, electrochemical, PEC water splitting, and right now, only electrolysis of water is present at the

commercial level [20]. But, hydrogen production by using renewable electrolysis water splitting is very low as only 4% can be obtained by this method [21].

Therefore, the requirements of searching for sustainable alternative energy sources for the creation and the storage of energy have increased [22]. Water splitting is basically a process in which water is used to produce the hydrogen (H_2) and oxygen (O_2) gasses as this is the most economical and environmentally friendly method [23]. The process of electrolysis involves passing an electric current through water, which releases hydrogen (H_2) and oxygen (O_2), as water is widely available [22]. As it goes, a schematic depiction of the image is given below in the Figure 1.1, which shows how the conduction band and valance band shows the water splitting with the help of light.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the photocatalysis for the hydrogen or oxygen generation [24]
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1.2 Basic Principle of Electrochemical water splitting

As far as water splitting is concerned, two phenomena are essential to understand; one is oxygen evolution reaction called as OER that occurs at anode; because of the anodic potential and Hydrogen evolution reaction that also called $H_2O \rightarrow H_{2(g)} + \frac{1}{2} O_{2(g)} \rightarrow (1)$

And for water splitting, two reactions are very important to understand as one reaction depicts the reaction of HER and OER as given below in the equations (2) and (3) respectively:

as HER occurs at cathode; because of the cathodic potential [25]. In both of these OER is comparatively a slow process because of the 4 electrons to transfer while forming reaction intermediates [26]. Ruthenium oxide or iridium oxide is used for OER and platinum is used for the HER in the basic as well as acidic medium [27].

As HER reaction takes place at the cathode, and the OER reaction takes place at the anode as given in the above equations (2) and (3), respectively.

1.2.1 Mechanism of OER

The OER occurs in three different medias as alkaline, neutral as well acidic media [28]. The pH is highly involved this reaction as four electron-proton coupled reactions are involved in this reaction [29]. Four protons are obtained from two H_2O molecules are oxidized, and besides this Oxygen molecule is also obtained in two different medias like acidic as well as neutral media [30]. Further explanation about this reaction is understood with the following reactions [31];

With the help of electrochemistry of OER as their potentials can be seen according to reaction mixture.

Above given potential of photoanodic reaction is in an acidic solution electrolytic reaction, while below given photoanodic potential is given for the alkaline electrolytic reaction:

As far as the protic reactions are concerned, that are explained in the above given reactions, but for the aprotic reactions in which no Hydrogen and Oxygen bond is present in any solvent:

1.2.1 Oxygen evolution reaction by Ta_3N_5

The photoanodes are made up of the semiconductors [33]. As far as the properties of the photoanodes are concerned, it could absorb the maximum visible light from the sunlight, better ability to transfer the electrons to the other electrode [34]. Many techniques have been used to modify the photoanodic efficiency of the semiconductor; and doping with element, heterojunction and surface modification [35]. Semiconductors which match with these properties are include bismuth sulphide, bismuth vanadate, tungsten oxide, molybdenum oxide iron oxide, tantalum nitride and titanium oxide;

specifically, the property of high electron transfer and better absorption of light [36]. From all the techniques to increase the efficiency of photoanodes, heterojunction is very important for the better absorption of the light. This technique is being used to enhance the photoelectrochemical performance, as this heterojunction could efficiently separate the electron-hole (e^-/h^+), and maximum ultra-violet visible light absorption [37]. Despite this heterojunction, another important technique which can enhance the photoanodic response for the oxygen evolution response as with the help of co-catalyst [38].

The light falls out on the surface than degradation of the surface will occur and to overcome that specific problem, further surface modification of the OER catalysts suggested [39]. Many tandem PEC cells have been developed for better efficiency to produce 10% of Hydrogen, but most difficult thing in tandem PEC cells is designing of the stable photoanode OER for the evolution of oxygen under sunlight irradiation [40]. For this purpose, Tantalum nitride is a better photoanode for oxygen evolution during the water splitting method. But its stability is difficult to attain and photoconversion efficiency is low due to poor electrical mobility [41].

Light absorption is directly associated with the intrinsic properties like the carrier diffusion, electron and carrier transport of semiconductor Ta_3N_5 [42]. Semiconductor's electrolyte solution interface, catalytic activity and the mass transfer of electrons should also be ascertain to check water splitting efficiency [43]. Many electrolytes and the metal oxides have been used to dope the surface of semiconductor Tantalum Nitride to improve the PEC cells efficiency for more oxygen evolution from the cell. By using new more probes can be used to grow the water splitting efficiency of the cells as discussed in this paper [44].

2. Surface modifications

The PEC cells consist of two electrodes as photoanode and photocathode. The efficiency of

these cells can be increased. This review totally emphasizes the total emphasize on the surface modification of the Tantalum Nitride semiconductor. Many electrocatalysts likewise Nickel, Iron and Cobalt species were doped on the surface of Ta_3N_5 semiconductor to see the effects of PEC cells and its efficiency [45].

2.1 SiO_2 Doping

Tantalum nitride (Ta_3N_5) has received importance due to the minimum energy level of CB and maximum energy level of VB, which lead to absorption of visible light that's why efforts have made to construct the semiconductors which are responsive to visible light [46].

Ta_3N_5 doped with the Aluminium and the Tantalum doping, both are the photocathode which are special in absorptive wavelength of 780 nm for water splitting [47]. In order to make tandem PEC cells, both sides of transparent Ta_3N_5 doped with the SiO_2 as discussed earlier that tandem semiconductor efficiency is much better than the parallel PEC cell so that's why transparent Ta_3N_5 is made tandem. Therefore, current study leads to the main point that the tandem PEC cells now have two sides as one side acts as photoanode and the back side acts as photocathode while using semiconductor Ta_3N_5 doped with SiO_2 [48].

2.2 Metal Oxide Doping

Its stability and photoconversion can be enhanced with the help of surface modification as nanostructure designing and doping of semiconductor with the other metal, because by doing this thickness of semiconductor has also impact on the PEC cells [49]. But with the thicker photoelectrode, problem usually happens of poorer charge-transfer ability due to factor of light scattering and reflection. In this study, it was noticed that nano films of PEC cells have much better efficiency as water splitting is on the 240 nm while thicker PEC cells showed very lower performance at 750nm as increased charge recombination rate [50].

In this study, problems of PEC cells were improved, as various cells with various thickness were prepared as by oxidation and nitridation of

the Ta foils. As far as semiconductor photoanodes are concerned, two different thickened photoanodes Ta_2O_5 and Ta_3N_5 , Tantalum nitride show less attachment to the substances, so to sort out this problem, porous structure has been developed as lesser light will reflect out and scattering will also be decreased and porous surface will allow more co-catalyst addition to the surface [51].

Ta_3N_5 Tantalum nitride (Ta_3N_5) has been widely used because of the small energy gap which is 2.1 eV as well as stability. Other significant property of this semiconductor is that it does not need any sort of assist for solar water splitting as other electrodes required assist to do water splitting and its splitting of water is spontaneous as a single photoanode [52]. Tantalum nitride oxides photocurrent potential curves are shown in the below given diagram for Nickel Iron cobalt oxides, Nickel Iron oxides, Cobalt oxides, Nickel oxides, and Iron oxides which are for the oxygen evolution reaction, as simulated sunlight Ta_3N_5 photoanodes generated anodic current. While using all these oxides, current production can be increased as increase the photoelectrode potential [53]. NiFeCoOx, NiFeOx oxides surface modification has set up the photocurrent potential to 0.7 comparatively vs RHE. If these oxides are compared with the $NiO_x / Ta_3N_5 / Ta$ photoanode has increased linearly, while hole transfer efficiency for NiOx is weak as compared to the mixed metal oxides as mentioned above [52]. As far as the oxides of FeOx are concerned, its photoanode show low photocurrent as compared to the Ta_3N_5 / Ta to get the oxygen evolution reaction, as light absorption in the FeOx is very insignificant, because it shows Iron oxide's light halting does not cause the low PEC cell's performance.

The performance of different photoanodes like NiFeCoOx/ Ta_3N_5 / Ta , CoOx/ Ta_3N_5 / Ta and NiFeOx Ta_3N_5 / Ta measured at the 0.7 vs. RHE under the simulated light, and it is reported Nickel Iron oxide was able to generate the 0.36 mAcm^{-2} photoanodic current density after 1 minute, which decreased after 5 minutes. NiFeOx/ Ta_3N_5 / Ta could also generate the photoanodic current density of 0.40 mAcm^{-2} after 1 minute, and that was

retained up to 0.36mAcm^{-2} after 5 minutes. It is much lower current density comparatively to other photoanodes of 0.03mAcm^{-2} was generated by the $\text{CoOx}/\text{Ta}_3\text{N}_5/\text{Ta}$. The photocurrent density can be increased by surface modification of the Ta_3N_5 through Co(OH)_x co-catalyst that is 2.8mA/cm^2 [53]. Co(OH)_x was coated on Tantalum nitride by impregnation method.

2. Nano-structuring of Ta_3N_5

Ta_3N_5 has poor charge transport and lesser $\text{CoPi}/\text{Ta}_3\text{N}_5/\text{Ta}$ light energy positions to get the absorption bands of long wavelength light, efficient charge separation bulk and surface defects absorption [54]. Therefore, to overcome this suffering as morphology control with a 1D configuration, such as nanotubes (NTs), nanorods' (NRs) and all these strategies advances the charge transfer to the solid-liquid interface with high absorption of light [55]. For this this reason, different nano structuring and morphology is being discussed here.

2.1 Ta_3N_5 Films

The expected results of photocatalytic activity can be obtained by the interface between electrolyte and semiconductor to produce the charges, and the second important tool that is to accelerate this charge across the interface [56]. Basically, co-catalysts are deposited on the Ta_3N_5 for the charge transferring between the electrolyte and semiconductor. The important co-catalysts that are used to produce the photogenerated holes in the Ta_3N_5 and also avoid the electrons to recombine with the catalysts surface for the efficient oxygen evolution reaction [57]. This includes Iron (III) oxide hydroxide, Nickle Iron layered double layer, cobalt hydroxide, and cobalt-principle investigator (CoPi) to generate and avoiding holes to recombine with the Ta_3N_5 [58]. It is reported in a study that the more active co-catalyst which can improve the efficiency of the interface charge transformation $\text{Co-Pi}/\text{GaN}$ bilayer. This heterojunction combination of the Ta_3N_5 and cobalt hydroxide can lead to the maximum solar water splitting [59]. For maximum solar water splitting, cobalt based co catalysts are considered as the most efficient co-catalysts. The one

condition which makes it the efficient co-catalyst is the basic ratio of $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{3+}$ in the cobalt oxide [60]. Furthermore, the plasma treatment also increases the solar water splitting by creating the maximum vacancies [61].

Ta_3N_5 is basically an n-type photoanode for water splitting, with the band gap of 2.1 eV which ultimately lead to the maximum current density [62]. The main motive behind the synthesis of the tantalum films is the excessive energy usage, because the substrates are need to expose the ammonia at the $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with the very weak adhesion. Therefore, due to this weak adhesion, the conductivity of the substrates Ta_3N_5 become very low [63]. This problem is sorted out by the atomic layer deposition (ALD) by preparing the tantalum doped films and depositing these films on the TTO (TiO_2). The synthesized films are amorphous at first, but this surface is further improved by the nitridation of the amorphous films of the tantalum nitride [64].

$\text{Ta}_3\text{N}_5/\text{GaN}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ are the crystal clear designated 600 nano meter absorption limit of the Ta_3N_5 . Ta_3N_5 films were prepared substrate by radiofrequency (RF) with the help of sputtering and this spiting focus was a Tantalum disk with a 50 nm diameter and a thickness of 3mm and Argon atmosphere for no less than ten mins for cleaning purpose [65]. By using quartz including quartz SiO_2 and bare sapphire Al_2O_3 , thin films transparent Ta_3N_5 were prepared resulting high transparency above 600 nm [64].

2.1 Ta_3N_5 Nanoflowers

Ta_3N_5 nanoflowers can be prepared through a simple hydrothermal method [66]. The nanosized structures preparation of the photocatalyst is only way possible to increase the photocatalytic activity by the heterojunction [67]. Therefore, this nanoflower structure is made by combining the semiconductors like Iridium oxide, cobalt oxide, tantalum oxide nitrate and silver nitrate with the Ta_3N_5 by the heterojunction method [68]. Basically, the deposition of the metals like silver, gold and platinum on the Ta_3N_5 increases the photocatalytic activity [69]. The nonwoven clothes of the Ta_3N_5 are prepared in one study with the help of $\text{Ta}_3\text{N}_5\text{-Pt}$ heterojunction, because this is the effective tool to increase the photocatalytic

activity [70]. A possible mechanism for the synthesis of Ta_3N_5 nanoflowers are done with the heterojunction of Ta_3N_5 -Au coupling to improve the photocatalytic activity [71].

As far as the main reactants are concerned for the synthesis, tantalum oxide, tantalum chloride are added into the Teflon heated at the temperature of $850\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with the solvothermal method. The

temperature range is very important for the synthesis of flower-like nanostructures of the Ta_3N_5 [72]. The heterojunction flower-like structure of the Ta_3N_5 -Au is via the Facile wet impregnation method by using the microspheres of the main catalyst [73]. Furthermore, the flower-like preparation of the electrocatalyst is demonstrated in the below given Figure 2.1.

Figure 2. Schematic preparation of the Flower-like nanostructure of Ta_3N_5 -Au [71] Produced Under common creative license 3.0.

This type of nanostructures includes Ta_3N_5 -Au, Ta_3N_5 -Pt, Ta_3N_5 -Ag, SiO_2 -Au and bulk Ta_3N_5 . In the given study, photocatalytic activity of these

nanosized structures is calculated by the degradation of the MB i.e., methylene blue after reaction of 60 minutes [74].

Catalyst

Degrading %age of MB

Bulk Ta_3N_5	60.3
Flower-like Ta_3N_5	76.1
Bulk Ta_3N_5 -Au	81.7
Flower-like Ta_3N_5 -Au	100

Consequently, different nanosized structures of the Ta_3N_5 are compared to improve the photocatalytic activity. Flower-like nanostructures showed better photocatalytic activity than the bulk Ta_3N_5 . The flower-like structure of Flower-like Ta_3N_5 -Au exhibited high degradation of the methylene blue (MB) in the time of 60 minutes reaction.

2.3 Olive-like structures Ta_3N_5

It is reported that Olive-like structure of Ta_3N_5 is prepared with the help of hydrothermal method in which Tantalum chloride and sodium amide [75]. The main reactants, as both these are heated at $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 hours, then calcination at $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours to obtain the final product [76]. The explanation of the hydrothermal method is given in the following paragraph. The controlled

nanostructure like olive-like structure of Ta_3N_5 and high purity simple oxides and nano sized spinel can be prepared with this hydrothermal method as its morphology can be adjusted the reaction's temperature and pressure [76]. For the preparation of this method, With the help of continuous stirring of aqueous solution KOH or NaOH are mixed with the metal salts which includes acetate, chloride and nitrate, then this mixture is autoclaved in which the solvent is sealed and heated for several hours to obtain the products [77].

The photocatalytic activity of the olive-like porous structure of Ta_3N_5 is assessed on the base of the catalytic degradation of the methylene blue (MB), just like the flower-like structure showed the activity on the degradation process [78]. Therefore, the hydrothermally synthesized materials

exhibited the higher degradation of the Ta_3N_5 under the visible light [79]. Another study was conducted on the degradation of the phenol by the porous material of Ta_3N_5 , as confirmed by the different morphological techniques [80]. It is reported in the study that the porous materials i.e., olive like structure of the exhibited higher degradation of the methylene blue (MB) and phenol as compared to the rod-like structure of the nanocomposites of Ta_3N_5 [81].

2.4 Micro-sheets of Ta_3N_5

Other composites are the micro sheets of Ta_3N_5 that can be prepared by various ways, but most promising methods are hydrothermal, template assisted synthesis and solvothermal method [82]. As far as the template assisted synthesis is concerned, it is being prepared with the help of ammonium metavanadate as a template, as these sheets gave the thickness of 100 nm, a length of several micro sheets [83]. The purpose of using this template so that the length of the nanocrystals of the Ta_3N_5 crystals can be controlled [84]. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) are used as the template in the method of chemical reduction method for the preparation of the Ta_3N_5 in the form of micro sheets [85].

This the method to make metal nanoparticles, a reducing agent is dissolved in water, often sodium borohydride [86]. Reducing agents are sometimes mixed with stabilizing agents [87]. Absorbance analysis examined the dispersion stability of metal nanoparticles. There are a number of drawbacks that are connected with reducing agents, including their toxicity, increased price, limited capacity to reduce, high costs, and impurities [88].

2.5 Dumbbell-like Nanostructures of Ta_3N_5

Dumbbell-like nanostructures of Ta_3N_5 have been synthesized using various methods. One such method is the hydrothermal synthesis route [89]. In their study, $TaCl_5$ and urea were used as precursors, and the reaction was carried out in a Teflon-lined stain less steel autoclave at 200 °C for 24 h [90]. The dumbbell-like nanostructure of Ta_3N_5 is usually range of a diameter of 80-120 nm [89]. The synthesis of dumbbell-like Ta_3N_5 nanostructures is also possible by using a

solvothermal method and microwave-assisted hydrothermal method [78]. In these methods, the resulting product was a dumbbell-like nanostructure of Ta_3N_5 with a diameter range of 100-200 nm [78].

In summary, dumbbell-like nanostructures of Ta_3N_5 have been synthesized using various methods such as hydrothermal, solvothermal, and microwave-assisted hydrothermal methods [52]. The best among all methods, is hydrothermal method, because the nanocomposites is of the very narrow range and are considered good nanocomposites for the applications [91].

2.6 Ta_3N_5 Nanotubes

According to the recent studies, plasma-inscribed Cobalt oxide showed a high ratio of Co^{2+}/Co^{3+} with the help of higher current density and lower potential that was performed on the Ar-inscribed Cobalt oxide NSs with oxygen vacancies assigned to high Co^{2+} population with the active sites for Oxygen evolution reaction [92]. The interactive impression of depletion of recombination centre on the interface and high oxygen voids of Cobalt hydroxide showed in higher activity of the photoanodes for the Ta_3N_5 [93]. The $Co(OH)_x/Tantalum\ Nitride$ for the atomic ratio of Co^{2+}/Co^{3+} directs to the more Co^{2+} concentration can lead to the surface oxygen vacancies induced in the Ar plasma [94]. The Cobalt hydroxide electrode directs to the much better water splitting activity on Ar-plasma-treated $Co(OH)_x$ for OER [92]. Another important function of the Ar-plasma on the surface of nanotubes of Ta_3N_5 caused the less defect densities, and the comparative density of Co^{2+} and Co^{3+} is related to the oxygen voids [94].

2.7 Ta_3N_5 Nanoparticles

Solutions with low energy with nanoparticles are considered to be the better incorporator of the light [95]. Photocatalysts are used as a renewable energy materials [17]. Many materials are important like quantum dots, carbon-based and metal oxide nanoparticle materials [96]. It is reported in different studies about the nanoparticles of Tantalum nitride, as it demonstrated higher photocatalytic activity [97]. Different methods are undertaken for the

preparation of Ta_3N_5 nanoparticles, but the best of one is the diffusion of nitrogen on the surface of Tantalum oxide [98]. It is the potential candidate with the band gap of 2.08 eV [99].

The photocatalytic activity of the Ta_3N_5 nanoparticles is reported with the different agents [100]. The activity of the material is reported by the degradation of the organic pollutants [101]. The higher degradation reported is of the methylene blue with the nanoparticles of the Ta_3N_5 [102]. The nanoparticles are synthesised with the help of the carbon nitride C_3N_4 , which can act as template and nitrogen source [103].

In conclusion, Ta_3N_5 nanoparticles demonstrated the highest durability than any other nano structure of these material. It is considered to be the better material version for the OER and its stability.

3. Electrochemical measurements Parameters

The following important parameters are used to assess the electrochemical performance of the

electrocatalyst. All the details are given in the following data;

3.1 Over Potential for OER

The electrochemical activity, there's the phenomenon which is of great importance is the over potential. To reduce over potential, electro catalysts are being used for OER to lower the over-potential and increase the charge separation capacity [105]. NiFeOx is being used to generate the holes under light and the other important reason to use this electrocatalyst is that it lowers the over potential [106]. It is reported that the over potential of the single metals is high as compared to the other composites which are adhered to it [107]. Single metal in blue which is the hybrid nanocomposite is the great in terms of the over potential, while the multi-metal oxides are also in the good position for lowering the over-potential [108]. This study is to highlight the potential of Ta_3N_5 as an efficient catalyst for the OER and provide valuable insights into its electrochemical performance in terms of overpotential [106].

Figure 3. Schematic diagram shows the over potential of the metal nitrides, decreased after by surface modification with other composites [108]. Produced Under common creative license 3.0.

3.2 Tafel Slope for OER and Double-layer Capacitance

The Tafel slope plays a crucial role in understanding the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) kinetics. It provides valuable insights into the reaction mechanism and the electrochemical

behaviour of catalysts involved in water splitting processes. The Tafel slope is defined as the slope of the linear relationship between the logarithm of the OER current density and the applied overpotential. The Tafel slope for the oxygen

evolution reaction (OER) by Ta_3N_5 has been reported to be approximately 40-60 mV/dec [109]. Double layer capacitance refers to the charge storage capacity at the interface between an electrode and an electrolyte solution. [110] examined the electrochemical properties of Ta_3N_5 and demonstrated its high double layer

capacitance and charge storage capabilities. They utilized techniques like cyclic voltammetry and impedance spectroscopy to characterize the electrochemical behaviour of Ta_3N_5 electrodes. The different studies are reported in the following Table 3.1.

Table 1. Different Tafel slopes measurements for Substrate and catalyst Ta_3N_5 .

Catalyst	Tafel slope mV/ dec	Electrolytes
Elemental Pt	530	0.1 M H_2SO_4
NiFeOx	40	1.0 M NaOH
Co_3O_4	54	1 M KOH
RhOx/CoOx	40	0.1 M $Na_2S_2O_8$

1. Electrocatalytic Methods for Preparation of Catalysts

The preparation of the electrocatalyst for the Oxygen evolution could lead to increase its activity, because its importance in the evolution is very important. There are many methods for the preparation of electrocatalyst as few of them are precipitation method, hydrothermal method, electrochemical methods, sol-gel method, and microwave assisted synthesis.

i. Hydrothermal Method

The controlled nanostructure and high purity simple oxides and nano sized spinel can be prepared with this hydrothermal method. The morphology of the nanoparticles can be adjusted the reaction temperature and pressure. The aqueous solution KOH or NaOH are mixed with the metal salts which includes acetate, chloride and nitrate, then this mixture is autoclaved in which the solvent is sealed and heated for several hours to obtain the products [77].

According to the stoichiometric technique, Ferrous ammonium sulphate and nickel sulphate were mixed up, and then this solvent mixture added into the autoclave which is prepared with the Teflon-lined stainless steel at temperature of 150 °C, where oxide is annealed with the help of high temperature and high pressure.

The nanosheets on which Manganese and Cobalt substituted with Iron oxide nanoparticles by Facile

hydrothermal method. Solvents are used in this method like ethylene glycol, isopropanol, Ethanol, dimethylformamide (DMF) and tertiary butanol.

ii. Solution-phase methods

The preparation of high yield mass production can be done by using this method. This method is also very promising with low temperature for the shape control, surface functionalization and hybridization [111]. One solution phase method for the preparation of Ta_3N_5 is the hydrothermal method. This involves the reaction of tantalum precursor and nitrogen source in an aqueous solution under high pressure and temperature. This method has been reported to produce high purity Ta_3N_5 with a well-defined morphology and high photocatalytic activity [112]. For instance, reported the preparation of Ta_3N_5 using the hydrothermal method. In their study, tantalum ethoxide and urea were used as the precursor and nitrogen source, respectively. The mixture was stirred and heated in an autoclave at 200°C for 24 hours. This study reported a high purity Ta_3N_5 product with a specific surface area of 42.8 m²/g and high photocatalytic activity for the degradation of organic pollutants [113]. Similarly, it is reported the preparation of Ta_3N_5 using a hydrothermal method with tantalum pentoxide and urea as the precursor and nitrogen source, respectively for the degradation of methylene blue [112].

Solution-phase method in which the different processes which are being takes place like polymerisation, condensation, solvent evaporation and annealing. This method is usually taken for the production of materials on larger commercial scale i.e., industrial scale.

iii. Sol-gel Method

Sol-gel method is an environment friendly method for the synthesis of nanomaterials [115]. High purity and high-quality nanoparticles can be synthesized by this method. Sol-gel process involves the transition of a solution system from a liquid sol into a solid phase [116]. That is a sol is converted into gel phase. For the heating treatment the solution placed at hot plate and heating will continue till to the critical temperature where auto combustion takes place and the final gel burnout then we get a fine powder [117]. This is low-cost, simple and reliable way for the synthetization of alloy, composite, ceramic, organic and inorganic sample [118]. It is not time-consuming process, and also it is magnificent stoichiometric controllable method [119]. The material formed highly pure, as multi component, it's a homogenous mixing. At a very low temperature as compared to other techniques auto combustion takes place [120]. The sol-gel method is a popular technique for the preparation of various materials, including Ta_3N_5 . A sol is prepared by mixing metal precursors with a solvent, followed by hydrolysis and condensation reactions. The resulting gel is then heated to obtain the desired material [121].

Nanosized can be prepared with the help of sol-gel method, because this is a fast, easy and fair methods. Multicomponent systems that is homogenous system works on the low processing and stoichiometric control method has advantages over the other methods [122]. Chelating agents which include $C_6H_8O_7$, $C_{10}H_{16}N_2O_8$, $C_3H_6O_2$, $C_2H_6O_2$, $C_2H_5NO_2$, CH_3COOH , Pluronic-123 (P123), or $C_6H_6O_2 / CH_2O$ in the metal salts, to form a homogeneous solution. For the obtaining of the final product, calcination is done, like in different studies this sol-gel method for the formation $NiFe_2O_4$, $CoFe_2O_4$, and $CoNiFe_2O_4$ in the oxygen evolution reaction [123].

iv. Chemical Reduction Method

The chemical reduction method for the preparation of Ta_3N_5 involves the reduction of tantalum pentoxide (Ta_2O_5) using ammonia (NH_3) gas as the reducing agent. The reaction takes place at high temperature and pressure in a sealed reactor. The Ta_3N_5 product is obtained as a black powder. One study that describes the chemical reduction method for the preparation of Ta_3N_5 [124].

This the method to make metal nanoparticles, a reducing agent is dissolved in water, often sodium borohydride. Reducing agents are sometimes mixed with stabilizing agents. Absorbance analysis examined the dispersion stability of metal nanoparticles. There are a number of drawbacks that are connected with reducing agents, including their toxicity, increased price, limited capacity to reduce, high costs, and impurities.

v. Precipitation Method

The precipitation method for the preparation of Ta_3N_5 involves the precipitation of tantalum ions from a solution followed by the thermal treatment of the precipitate to form the nitride. One study by [125] described the preparation of Ta_3N_5 by the precipitation method using ammonium bicarbonate as the precipitant. Metal oxide nanoparticles are prepared in this method, which is not inclined for any special equipment, or a complicated process, as it is used to control the particle size and shape, and at the end different constituents are mixed thoroughly in this method [127]. In recent studies, to get the high electrocatalyst cavity, this method is followed as $MnSO_4 \cdot H_2O$, $CrCl_3$ and $(NH_4)_2Fe(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ along with Manganese ferrites in which Cr was replaced with the Manganese ferrites in which NaOH was added at the end [128].

vi. Electrochemical Method

One electrochemical method for the preparation of Ta_3N_5 involves the use of Ta metal as the starting material and an electrolyte consisting of NH_4Cl and NH_4F . This method was described in a study by [129] who reported the synthesis of Ta_3N_5 nanoparticles using a cyclic voltammetry technique. In this method, a Ta electrode is used

as the working electrode and a Pt wire and Ag/AgCl electrode are used as the counter and reference electrodes, respectively [130]. The cyclic voltammetry technique is used to repeatedly apply a potential range of -0.6 V to 0.8 V vs. Ag/AgCl to the Ta electrode, causing the formation of Ta_3N_5 nanoparticles on the surface of the electrode. The resulting Ta_3N_5 nanoparticles are then collected by ultrasonically treating the electrode in water [130]. This study demonstrated that the electrochemical synthesis of Ta_3N_5 nanoparticles was highly efficient and could be easily scaled up for large-scale production [130].

vii. Electrospinning Method

Electrospinning method is famous for the synthesis of the nanofibers from the polymers, ceramics and polymers [131]. This method has gained much importance in the recent studies, because of, high electrocatalytic activity, mass transformed, and high surface area [132]. A precursor is required to prepare the nanofibers. To be more precise, Electrospinning process is explained with the help of the given Figure 2.1. A high voltage connected syringe is used to load the precursor with a metallic needle. The voltage range usually varies between 5 to 30 kV [133]. Syringe which is ejecting the precursor onto the collector, and leading towards the formation of the nanofibers of the Ta_3N_5 on the nonwoven mat. It is also depicted the electrospinning method for the

preparation the nanofibers after calcinating solvothermal reaction.

Ta_3N_5 is being formed with the help of electrospinning method for various applications, including photocatalysis, water splitting, and energy storage. One study that utilized electrospinning for the preparation of Ta_3N_5 [134]. Ta_3N_5 nanofibers were prepared using a simple electrospinning technique followed by thermal treatment. The resulting Ta_3N_5 nanofibers exhibited excellent photocatalytic activity for the degradation of Rhodamine B under visible light irradiation [135]. The reason behind the excellent photocatalytic activity of the nanofibers is the narrow band gap, for the absorption of visible light photons. Another important logic for the excellent activity is of the high surface area of the electro spun Ta_3N_5 fibres [136]. Furthermore, photocatalytic activity can also be increased with the help of nano composition of these fibres with the carbon-based materials or metal nano particles. The last but not the least, operating conditions likewise concentrations, temperature and pH can also further increase the photocatalytic activity [137].

In conclusion, electro spun nanofibers are considered to be the long-term stable and reusability of the materials. Multiple tests have been done to demonstrate the photocatalytic stability by the degradation of the Rhodamine B under the irradiation of the visible light [138].

Figure 4. Schematic diagram for the preparation of Ta_3N_5 and Bi_2WO_6 [139]. Produced Under common creative license 3.0.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the above reported studies that photoanodic Ta₃N₅ has shown promising result for the OER as a critical process. If other metals or non-metals introduced on the surface of the related photoanode Ta₃N₅ can increase the oxygen evolution by generating more active sites. The reported non-metals material can increase the OER is SiO₂. It is also reported the OER performance can be enhanced by surface modification of the Ta₃N₅ as cobalt, nickel, or iron oxide has been found to significantly improve the OER performance of Ta₃N₅. In addition, Pt, RuO₂, or IrO₂ are the co-catalysts are used for the further enhancement of OER. These co-catalysts can effectively promote the charge transfer and reduce the overpotential required for OER.

Overall, it can be concluded that surface modification and co-catalyst deposition are effective strategies to enhance the OER performance of Ta₃N₅ and can lead to more efficient water splitting processes for sustainable energy production. However, further research is needed to optimize the synthesis and design of these modified Ta₃N₅ catalysts to achieve even better OER activity and stability.

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